

SQL TILI HAQIDA TUSHUNCHA

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu tezisda SQL tili haqida qisqacha ma'lumot berilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: SQL, utilitlar, operator, DDL, DML, DCL, ANSI

SQL(Structured Query Language) – Bu so'rov tili ko'p operatorlardan tashkil topgan bo'lib, bu operatorlar orqali foydalanuvchilar va dasturlar Oracle(MBBT) dagi ma'lumotlar bazasiga murojaatni amalga oshirishi mumkin. Oracle utililari yoki har xil dasturlar SQL operatorlarisiz bazaga murojaatni amalga oshirishi mumkin, lekin so'rovlarni amalga oshirishda bu so'rov tilidan foydalanmaslikning iloji yo'q.

1970 yil iyun oyida E. F. KODD o'zining E.F. Codd, "A Relational Model of Data for Large Shared Data Banks" maqolasini ommaga taqdim etdi. Bu maqola "Communications of the ACM" jurnalida chop etildi. Hozirgi kunda Koddning bu modeli "relyastion ma'lumotlar bazasini boshqarish tizimi(RMBBT)" ning yakuniy modeli deb qabul qilindi. Kodd ning modelni yo'lga qo'yish maqsadida IBM firmasi SEQUEL(Structured English Query Language) tilini ishlab chiqdi. Keyinchalik bu til SQL tiliga o'zgartirildi, lekin haligacha "sikvel" deb ham yuritilmoqda. 1979 yil Relational Software(hozirgi vaqtdagi Oracle) korporatsiyasi SQL ning birinchi tijoriy ishlanmasini ommaga taqdim etdi. Hozirgi kunda SQL tili RMBBTning standart tili hisoblanadi.

SQL tili so'rov-natija ko'rinishida ishlaydi. So'rovlar har bir element uchun emas, butun bir guruh uchun beriladi va natija olinadi. SQL uchun ma'lumotlar bazasidagi ma'lumotlar qay shaklda, qay tartibda joylashganini umuman ahamiyati yo'q, foydalanuvchilar ham bu ma'lumotlarni bilishi shart emas. Faqatgina operatorlarni to'g'ri yozish orqali istalgan ma'lumotlarni chiqarish mumkin bo'ladi.

SQL tili barcha ma'lumotlar bazasini boshqarish tizimlari uchun umumiy standart til hisoblanadi. Bundan kelib chiqadiki, agar siz bu tilni bir marotaba o'rganib olsangiz, istalgan MBBT lari bilan ishlay olasiz. Bitta MBBT da yaratilgan biror sql operatorlar yig'indisi(kichik so'rov dasturi)ni, istalgan MBBT ga ko'chirish mumkin bo'ladi.

SQL operatorlari orqali quyidagi vazifalarni bajarish mumkin:

Ma'lumotlarni so'rov orqali olish.

Jadvalning qatorlariga ma'lumot qo'shish, qatorlarini o'chirish va yangilash.

Ob'ektlarni yaratish, o'zgartirish va o'chirish.

Ma'lumotlar bazasi va ob'ektlarga ruxsatlarni o'rnatish.

Ma'lumotlar bazasi foydalanuvchilarini hosil qilish va baza xafsizligini ta'minlash.

2 hil turdagi SQL mavjud: interaktiv va o'rnatilgan(встроенный). SQL ning bu 2 turi ishlashi bir hil, lekin har xil joyda ishlatiladi.

Interaktiv SQL deganda — ma'lumotlar bazasiga so'rov orqali murojaat qilib, shu zahoti natijani olish tushuniladi. Ya'ni bunda ketma-ketlik asosida jarayon sodir bo'ladi. So'rov-natija rejimda ishlaydi.

O'rnatilgan SQL deganda – so'rovlar yig'indisi biror dasturlash tilida ishlatilishi tushuniladi. Pascal, Delphi, Java tillarida bazaga murojaat qilib, natijani biror o'zgaruvchiga yuklab qo'yamiz va kerakli joyda bu natijani ishlatamiz. Ya'ni bunda so'rov berib, darhol natijani

ololmaymiz. Natija faqat dasturning davom etishi uchun olinadi va talab etilgan joyda ishlatiladi.

SQL operatorlari bir necha guruhlariga bo'lingan. Bu bo'linish operatorlarning bajarilish vazifasi asosida bo'lingan. Ular quyidagilar:

DDL(Data Definition Language) , ANSI bu guruh SDL(Schema Definition Language) deb ataladi. Bu guruhga ma'lumotlar bazasida ob'ektlar(jadvallar, indekslar)ni hosil qiluvchi operatorlar kiradi.

DML(Data Manipulation Language) – ma'lumotlarni manipulyatsiya qiluvchi operatorlar yig'indisi guruhi. Iсталgan vaqtda jadval ichida qanday ma'lumotlar saqlanayotganini aniqlovchi operatorlar.

DCL(Data Control Language) – ma'lumotlarni boshqaruvchi operatorlar.

ANSI ning ruxsati bilan, DCL DDL ning bir qismi sifatida qaraladi. Bu guruhlarni aralashtirmaslik zarur. Bular alohida tillar emas, balki SQL operatorlarining guruhlaridir.

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